

Shifted Burr Type XII distribution for modeling asymmetric lifetime data

Jude Opara¹, Daa S. Metwally^{2*}, Chidimma Udo Osuagwu³, Caleb Chisom Ezeh⁴, Okechukwu J. Obulezi⁵, Hatem E. Semaary⁶, and Mohammed Elgarhy^{7,8}

¹Department of Mathematics & Computer Science, University of Africa, Toru-Orua Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Email: judend88@yahoo.com

²Deanship of Scientific Research, Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), Riyadh 11432, Saudi Arabia; dmetwally@imamu.edu.sa

³Department of Statistics, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Email: chidinmaosuagwu5@gmail.com

⁴Department of Statistics, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, P.O. Box, Awka, Nigeria. Email: cc.ezeh_7@stu.unizik.edu.ng

⁵Department of Statistics, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, P.O. Box, Awka, Nigeria. Email: oj.obulezi@unizik.edu.ng

⁶Department of Mathematics and Statistics, College of Science, Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), Riyadh, 11432, Saudi Arabia; hesemaary@imamu.edu.sa

⁷Faculty of Computers and Information Systems, Egyptian Chinese University, Nasr City, Egypt; dr.moelgarhy@gmail.com

⁸Department of Computer Engineering, Biruni University, 34010, Istanbul, Turkey; dr.moelgarhy@biruni.edu.tr

*Corresponding author email

Abstract

This study proposes the Shifted Burr Type XII (SHBXII) distribution, a flexible four parameter extension of the classical Burr XII model, achieved by incorporating a location parameter (δ) to handle data with non-zero thresholds. Key structural properties were derived, including the Probability Density Function, Cumulative Distribution Function, Hazard Function, Quantile Function, moments, Moment Generating Function, Renyi and Tsallis entropies, stochastic ordering, and order statistics. Seven non-Bayesian estimation methods were employed: Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE), Maximum Product of Spacing, Least Squares, Weighted Least Squares, Cramér–von Mises, Anderson–Darling, and Right-Tailed Anderson–Darling. Their performance was assessed via an extensive Monte Carlo simulation study across different parameter settings and sample sizes, using Bias and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) as metrics. The results demonstrated that the MLE method consistently provided the most accurate and efficient estimates, with its performance improving as sample size increased. The SHBXII was validated by applying it to a real-world dataset of observed waiting times. Its fit was compared with the standard Burr XII and Weibull distributions using information criteria like AIC, BIC,

and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The SHBXII exhibited a superior fit, shown by the lowest information criteria values and the highest K-S p-value (0.7428), which was further supported by graphical diagnostics. The study concludes that the SHBXII is a robust and effective model for analyzing lifetime and environmental data characterized by threshold effects.

Keywords— Shifted Burr Type XII (SHBXII) distribution, Location Parameter, Lifetime Distribution, Non-Zero Threshold

1 Introduction

Probability distributions are fundamental tools for statistical modeling, providing the framework to describe uncertainty and analyze data across numerous scientific fields. While classical models like the normal, exponential, and gamma distributions are widely used, they often lack the necessary flexibility to capture real-life phenomena that exhibit strong skewness and heavy tails [1]. This deficiency has driven the development of generalized distribution families with additional parameters to improve modeling accuracy [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The recent focus on creating new and extended lifetime distributions highlights the ongoing need for flexible tools in applied statistics [7, 8, 9].

The Burr Type XII (BXII) distribution [10], widely used in its three-parameter form (two shape, one scale), is a versatile model known for its ability to capture a broad range of density and hazard function shapes. It has been successfully applied in fields such as reliability engineering, actuarial science, survival analysis, and economics [11, 12]. Various modifications and generalizations of the Burr family have been proposed to enhance tail behavior or address complex data structures [13, 14, 15, 16].

However, despite its inherited flexibility, the standard BXII distribution is fundamentally restricted by its lack of a location (shift) parameter. This critical absence limits its application to datasets that strictly start at zero. In many real-world scenarios, data naturally begin after a nonzero threshold ($\delta > 0$). For instance, in reliability analysis, a device's recorded lifetime may only start after a guaranteed minimum life or 'burn-in' period. In finance and insurance are often only reported when they exceed a deductible threshold. The standard BXII cannot accurately account for this non-zero starting point, forcing the scale and shape parameters to unduly compensate, which negatively impacts the quality of the statistical fit and the interpretability of the model. None of the current extensions directly and robustly address the practical necessity of incorporating a flexible location parameter.

This study is motivated by the need to resolve this critical boundary limitation. The novelty of this work lies in the proposal and comprehensive analysis of the four-parameter Shifted Burr Type XII (SHBXII) distribution. The SHBXII extends the classical three-parameter BXII by uniquely incorporating a location parameter (δ).

The inclusion of (δ) offers substantial advantages:

- It formally accommodates a non-zero minimum threshold, making the model applicable to a vast class of threshold-based datasets.
- It provides a physical interpretation in reliability analysis, modeling a guaranteed life (δ).
- It is a true generalization, as the standard BXII is a special case when ($\delta = 0$), and it offers a direct statistical mechanism to test the null hypothesis of a zero threshold ($\delta = 0$).
- By statistically decoupling the distribution's support from its scale, the SHBXII achieves superior modeling flexibility and parameter interpretability compared to its unshifted counterpart.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 formally defines the SHBXII distribution and specifies its fundamental mathematical functions, including the probability density function and, cumulative distribution function. Section 3 focuses on the study of the properties. In section 4, we estimate the parameters using some classical methods. In Section 5, a comprehensive simulation study is carried out to determine the performance of the estimators in the presence of small and large sample sizes. In Section 6, we demonstrate the applicability of the proposed SHBXII model using two lifetime datasets. Section 7 concludes the study with limitations identified and future works proposed.

2 Specification of the SHBXII

Burr [10] proposed the two-parameter Burr XII distribution, which is flexible as a log-normal distribution, but was later parametrized into a three-parameter distribution by adding a scale parameter. Its probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF), respectively, are given as

$$f(x; c, k, \lambda) = \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-(k+1)}, \quad (1)$$

and,

$$F(x; c, k, \lambda) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}. \quad (2)$$

The concept of a shift or location parameter is old in the statistical literature. It is like a hedge in financial principle that implies changing origin to a preferred data point. Suppose the random variable $X \sim \text{BurrXII}(c, k, \lambda)$ has a shift parameter δ , such that $y \geq \delta$ and $\delta > 0$. That is $Y = X + \delta$, then $Y \sim \text{SHBXII}(\delta, c, k, \lambda)$ having PDF and CDF, respectively, given as follows.

$$f(y) = \frac{ck}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{k+1}}; \quad y \geq \delta, \lambda > 0, \delta > 0, \quad (3)$$

and

$$F(y) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}. \quad (4)$$

In modeling lifetime data, the survival function and hazard rate function are essentially used to depict the reliability and extinction of the exposed population. The survival function is $S(y) = 1 - CDF$. Hence;

$$S(y) = \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k} \quad (5)$$

and the hazard rate function is given by;

$$h(y) = \frac{f(y)}{S(y)} = \frac{\frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k-1}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}} = \frac{ck \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1}}{\lambda \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]}. \quad (6)$$

The asymptotic behavior for the SHBXII distribution with PDF, CDF, and hazard function given in (2),(4), and (6) is given by;

First, taking limits, we obtain:

For the PDF:

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \delta^+} f(y) = \begin{cases} \infty, & 0 < c < 1, \\ \frac{ck}{\lambda}, & c = 1, \\ 0, & c > 1, \end{cases} \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} f(y) = 0.$$

For the CDF:

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \delta^+} F(y) = 0, \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} F(y) = 1.$$

For the hazard rate function:

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \delta^+} h(y) = \begin{cases} \infty, & 0 < c < 1, \\ \frac{k}{\lambda}, & c = 1, \\ 0, & c > 1, \end{cases} \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} h(y) = 0.$$

This shows that the PDF of the SHBXII is heavy-tailed and may diverge at the threshold δ , while the CDF increases smoothly from 0 to 1, and the hazard is decreasing for $0 < c \leq 1$ but unimodal for $c > 1$. It increases from 0, attains a maximum at

$$y_{\text{mode}} = \delta + \lambda \left(\frac{c-1}{ck+1} \right)^{1/c},$$

and then decreases to 0 as $y \rightarrow \infty$.

Figure 1: PDF of SHBXII (δ, c, k, λ).

The plots in figure 1 show that the SHBXII distribution has L-shape, unimodal shape and an monotonically decreasing shape.

Figure 2: pdf 3D plots of the SHBXII (δ, c, k, λ) .

figure 2 shows the 3D plots of the SHBXII.

Figure 3: Hazard plots of the SHBXII (δ, c, k, λ) .

The plots of the hazard function shown in Figure 3, have a monotonically decreasing, strictly increasing, unimodal shape and reversed bathtub profiles.

3 Properties of the SHBXII distribution

In this section we derive some useful mathematical properties of the proposed Shifted Burr type XII Distribution.

3.1 Crude Moment

Let $Y \sim \text{SHBXII}(\delta, \lambda; c, k)$ with PDF in (2), then the r^{th} crude moment of the Shifted Burr Type XII Distribution is given as;

$$\mu^r = \sum_{i=0}^r \binom{r}{i} \delta^{r-i} \lambda^i k \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{i}{c} + 1) \Gamma(k - \frac{i}{c})}{\Gamma(k)} \right). \quad (7)$$

Proof : The r^{th} crude moment is conventionally defined as;

$$\mu'_r = E(Y^r) = \int_{\delta}^{\infty} y^r f(y) dy, \quad (8)$$

where $f(y)$ is the PDF defined for the random variable Y . Inserting eqn (2) into eqn (8), the r^{th} crude moment for the SHBXII can therefore be expressed as;

$$\mu'_r = E(Y^r) = \int_{\delta}^{\infty} (x + \delta)^r \frac{ck}{\lambda} \frac{\left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{k+1}} dy. \quad (9)$$

Let $x = \frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \Rightarrow y = \lambda x + \delta$, and $dy = \lambda dx$, then;

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_r &= \sum_{i=0}^r \binom{r}{i} \delta^{r-i} \lambda^i k \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{i}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{i}{c}\right)}{k \Gamma(k)} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^r \binom{r}{i} \delta^{r-i} \lambda^i \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{i}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{i}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)}. \end{aligned}$$

The mean of the SHBXII is obtained by substituting $r = 1$ in equation (7). That is,

$$E[Y] = \lambda \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} + \delta. \quad (10)$$

The 2^{nd} , 3^{rd} and 4^{th} moments about the origin are given below,

$$\mu'_2 = \lambda^2 \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \right) + 2\delta\lambda \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \right) + \delta^2. \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_3 &= \lambda^3 \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{3}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \right) + 3\delta\lambda^2 \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \right) \\ &\quad + 3\delta^2\lambda \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \right) + \delta^3. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_4 &= \lambda^4 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{4}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{4}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} + 4\delta\lambda^3 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{3}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} \\ &\quad + 6\delta^2\lambda^2 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} + 4\delta^3\lambda \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(k)} + \delta^4. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

3.2 Central Moments

Let $Y \sim SHBXII(\delta, \lambda; c, k)$. The 2nd, 3rd, and 4th central moments corresponding to the variance, skewness, and kurtosis, respectively, can be obtained as follows.

Let $P_r = \frac{\lambda^r}{\Gamma(k)}$, for $r = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Therefore;

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_2 &= \text{Var}(Y) \\ &= P_2 \Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right) - \left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right)^2.\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_3 &= \mu'_3 - 3\mu'_2\mu'_1 + 2(\mu'_1)^3 \\ &= P_3 \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{3}{c}\right) \\ &\quad - 3\left(P_2 \Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right)\right) \left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right) \\ &\quad + 2\left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right)^3.\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_4 &= \mu'_4 - 4\mu'_3\mu'_1 + 6\mu'_2(\mu'_1)^2 - 3(\mu'_1)^4 \\ &= P_4 \Gamma\left(\frac{4}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{4}{c}\right) \\ &\quad - 4\left(P_3 \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{3}{c}\right)\right) \left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right) \\ &\quad + 6\left(P_2 \Gamma\left(\frac{2}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{2}{c}\right)\right) \left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right)^2 \\ &\quad - 3\left(P_1 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{c} + 1\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{1}{c}\right)\right)^4.\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

Therefore, the coefficient of skewness and kurtosis is given respectively as;

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\mu_3}{\sigma^3} \text{ and } \gamma_2 = \frac{\mu_4}{\sigma^4}$$

3.3 Mode

The mode y_0 of the SHBXII distribution is obtained by first taking the derivative of the PDF and equating it to zero.

Put $y - \delta = x$, therefore;

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dx} f(x) &= \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{-(k+1)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{ck}{\lambda} (c-1) \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{k+1} - \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c c(k+1) \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^k}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{2(k+1)}} = 0 \\ &= \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left\{ (c-1) \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^{k+1} - \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c c(k+1) \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^k \right\} = 0.\end{aligned}\tag{17}$$

Factor out common terms from the numerator;

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{c-2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^k \left[(c-1) \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right) - (k+1)c \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c \right] = 0 \\ &= (c-1) \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c\right) - (k+1)c \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Solve for x ;

$$\left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^c = \frac{c-1}{ck+1} \quad \implies \quad x = \lambda \left(\frac{c-1}{ck+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{c}}.$$

Recall that $x = y - \delta$, Hence;

$$y = \delta + \lambda \left(\frac{c-1}{ck+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{c}}.$$

3.4 Mean residual life function

Given that a component has survived until time t , the expected additional lifetime is called the mean residual lifetime. And for a continuous distribution with PDF $f(y)$ and CDF $F(y)$, the mean residual function is given by;

$$\begin{aligned} m(y) &= E(Y - y | Y > y) = \frac{1}{1 - F(y)} \int_y^\infty (1 - F(t)) dt \quad (18) \\ &= \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^k \int_x^\infty \frac{1}{(1+t^c)^k} dt. \end{aligned}$$

letting $x = \frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}$, and $u = t^c$, we have;

$$= \frac{1}{c} (1+x^c)^k \cdot \int_{x^c}^\infty u^{\frac{1}{c}-1} (1+u)^{-k} du.$$

This integral can further be expressed using the incomplete beta function, expressed as $\beta_z(a, b)$, given by;

$$\beta_z(a, b) = \frac{1}{c} \Gamma_{\frac{1}{1+x^c}} \left(k - \frac{1}{c}, \frac{1}{c}\right). \quad (19)$$

hence the MRL function becomes;

$$\frac{1}{c} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right)^k \cdot \frac{1}{c} \Gamma_{\frac{1}{1+\left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c}} \left(k - \frac{1}{c}, \frac{1}{c}\right). \quad (20)$$

3.5 Quantile Function

The quantile function (QF) of the SHBXII distribution is

$$Y = \delta + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{(1-p)^k} - 1 \right)^{1/c}.$$

3.6 Stress-Strength Reliability analysis

The hazard rate function of the Shifted Burr XII ($y; \delta, \lambda, c, k$) distribution is given by $h_y = \frac{f_Y(y)}{1-F_Y(y)}$ where;

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-(k+1)}; \quad y \geq \delta, \quad \delta > 0,$$

and

$$F_Y(y) = 1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-k}; \quad \delta > 0.$$

And the reliability function $R(y)$ denoted by $(1 - F_Y(y)) = P(Y > y) = \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-k}$.

The stress strength reliability of a distribution is the probability that the strength $P(Y_1)$ is greater than the stress $P(Y_2)$ for all possible values of the stress (Y_2).

Here, we derive the reliability R when Y_1 and Y_2 are independent random variables distributed with parameters (c_1, k_1) and (c_2, k_2) , then,

$$R = P(Y_1 > Y_2) = \int_{\delta}^{\infty} f_1(y) F_2(y) dy. \quad (21)$$

substituting the values of $f_1(y)$ and $F_2(y)$ into the integral, we have;

$$\begin{aligned} R &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{c_1 k_1}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_1-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_1} \right)^{-(k_1+1)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_2} \right)^{k_2}} \right) dy. \\ &= \frac{c_1 k_1}{\lambda} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_1-1}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_1} \right)^{k_1+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c_2} \right)^{k_2}} \right) dy. \end{aligned}$$

If $c_2 = c_1 = c$, Then

$$R = k_1 \left(\frac{\Gamma(1+k_1-c)}{\Gamma(1+k_1)} - \frac{\Gamma(1+k_1+k_2-c)}{\Gamma(1+k_1+k_2)} \right). \quad (22)$$

3.7 Renyi entropy

Rényi [17] introduced a generalized entropy by extending the concepts of uncertainty and randomness. The Rényi entropy, which generalizes Shannon's entropy, is parameterized by a single parameter, p . As p approaches unity, it converges to the familiar Shannon entropy. Xu and Erdogmuns [18] A notable property of Rényi entropy is that in algorithms requiring entropy maximization, Rényi's entropy can be substituted directly for Shannon's, as both entropies reach their maximum under the same conditions. The Rényi entropy is calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{en} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \left[\int_0^\infty (f^\alpha(y)) dy \right] \quad \alpha \geq 0, \alpha \neq 1 \quad (23)$$

$$= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \left[\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-(k+1)} \right)^\alpha dx \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \left[(ck)^\alpha \lambda^{-\alpha} \int_0^\infty \frac{\left(\left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \right)^\alpha}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{\alpha(k+1)}} dx \right]$$

$$R_{en} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \left[\frac{(ck)^\alpha}{c\lambda^\alpha} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha(c-1)+1}{c}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha(ck+1)-1}{c}\right)}{\Gamma(\alpha(k+1))} \right]. \quad (24)$$

The limit of the Renyi entropy as $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1}$ gives the Shannon entropy.

3.8 Tsallis entropy

For continuous distributions with probability density function $f(y)$, the Tsallis entropy is defined as;

$$T = \frac{1}{\alpha-1} \left[1 - \int_0^\infty (f^\alpha(u)) dy \right] \quad (25)$$

$$T = \frac{1 - (ck)^\alpha \lambda^{-\alpha} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha(c-1)+1}{c}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha(ck+1)-1}{c}\right)}{(\alpha-1)c\Gamma(k\alpha+k)}. \quad (26)$$

3.9 VaR measures

VaR (Value at Risk) sets a maximum loss threshold for a certain confidence level. Put otherwise, it offers an illustration of the magnitude of damages that surpass the worst-case scenario that is protected by VaR at the chosen level. Thus, for the SHBXII distribution, the quantile function is defined as follows:

$$\text{VaR}_q = \delta + \lambda \left[(1-q)^{-1/k} - 1 \right]^{1/c}, \quad 0 < q < 1, \quad (27)$$

where $P^{-1}(q)$ is the inverse of the cumulative distribution function of the SHBXII distribution.

3.10 TVaR measures

Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR), often referred to as Tail Value-at-Risk (TVaR), is a risk measure that provides the expected loss given that the Value at Risk (VaR) threshold has already been exceeded. While VaR specifies a quantile bound for potential losses at level q , TVaR goes further by averaging the losses beyond this bound. In other words, it gives a more comprehensive view of extreme tail risk. The TVaR $_q$ of the SHBXII distribution is correctly expressed in terms of the Incomplete Beta function:

$$\text{TVaR}_q = \delta + \frac{\lambda}{1-q} \left[B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B_u\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right], \quad (28)$$

where $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Beta function, $B_u(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Incomplete Beta function, and the integration limit is $u = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\text{VaR}_q - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-1}$.

Proof:

By definition,

$$\text{TVaR}_q = \frac{1}{1-q} \int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} yf(y) dy.$$

The integral term is the partial expectation of $X = \delta + \lambda Y$ (where $Y \sim \text{Burr XII}(c, k)$).

$$\int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} yf(y) dy = \delta \int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} f(y) dy + \lambda \int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} (y - \delta)f(y) dy,$$

Since $P(X > \text{VaR}_q) = 1 - q$, and $y_q = (\text{VaR}_q - \delta)/\lambda$:

$$\int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} yf(y) dy = \delta(1 - q) + \lambda [E[Y] - E[Y \cdot I(Y \leq y_q)]].$$

We use the known results for the Burr XII moments:

$$E[Y] = B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right).$$

The integral $\int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} (y - \delta)f(y) dy$ evaluates to the difference between the complete moment and the partial moment, which is expressed using the Incomplete Beta function B_u :

$$\int_{\text{VaR}_q}^{\infty} yf(y) dy = \delta(1 - q) + \lambda \left[B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B_u\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right],$$

Substituting this back into the TVaR_q definition and simplifying:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TVaR}_q &= \frac{1}{1-q} \left(\delta(1 - q) + \lambda \left[B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B_u\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right] \right) \\ \text{TVaR}_q &= \delta + \frac{\lambda}{1-q} \left[B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B_u\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

3.11 Gini Index

A population's inequality in the distribution of wealth or income is gauged by the Gini index. It is widely employed in economic research to evaluate the level of social inequality. For the SHBXII distribution, It is defined by the correct closed-form integral result:

$$GI = \frac{\lambda}{\mu_0 c} \left[B\left(\frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B\left(\frac{1}{c}, 2k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right],$$

with μ_0 being the first crude moment (the mean) given by $\mu_0 = \delta + \lambda B\left(1 + \frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right)$.

Proof: The Gini index is described as follows:

$$GI = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int_{\delta}^{\infty} F(y)(1 - F(y)) dy.$$

Using the SHBXII CDF with $z = \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c$:

$$\begin{aligned} F(y)(1 - F(y)) &= F(y) - F^2(y) \\ &= 1 - (1 + z)^{-k} - \left[1 - (1 + z)^{-k} \right]^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$= (1+z)^{-k} - (1+z)^{-2k}.$$

The integral of the numerator is $\int_{\delta}^{\infty} F(y)(1-F(y)) dy$. We use the change of variable $z = \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c$, so $dy = \frac{\lambda}{c} z^{\frac{1}{c}-1} dz$.

$$\int_{\delta}^{\infty} F(y)(1-F(y)) dy = \frac{\lambda}{c} \int_0^{\infty} [(1+z)^{-k} - (1+z)^{-2k}] z^{\frac{1}{c}-1} dz.$$

The integral is evaluated using the Beta function identity $B(a, b) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{u^{a-1}}{(1+u)^{a+b}} du$.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{z^{\frac{1}{c}-1}}{(1+z)^k} dz = B\left(\frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right),$$

and,

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{z^{\frac{1}{c}-1}}{(1+z)^{2k}} dz = B\left(\frac{1}{c}, 2k - \frac{1}{c}\right)$$

Substituting the correct integral result gives;

$$\int_{\delta}^{\infty} F(x)(1-F(x)) dx = \frac{\lambda}{c} \left[B\left(\frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B\left(\frac{1}{c}, 2k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right].$$

So the Gini index of the SHBXII is given by;

$$GI = \frac{\lambda}{\mu_0 c} \left[B\left(\frac{1}{c}, k - \frac{1}{c}\right) - B\left(\frac{1}{c}, 2k - \frac{1}{c}\right) \right].$$

3.12 Distribution of the Order Statistics

Suppose Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n is a random sample of Y ; $Y_{(r)}$ ($r = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are the r^{th} order statistics obtained by arranging Y_i in ascending order of magnitude

$$Y_1 \leq Y_2 \leq \dots \leq Y_r \leq \dots \leq Y_n,$$

and $Y_1 = \min(Y_1, \dots, Y_n)$, $Y_n = \max(Y_1, \dots, Y_n)$. The probability density function of the r^{th} order statistic is given by

$$f_{r:n}(y) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} f_Y(y) [F_Y(y)]^{r-1} [1-F_Y(y)]^{n-r}, \quad (29)$$

Substituting (2) and (4) into (29) gives the explicit form

$$\begin{aligned} f_{r:n}(y) &= \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-(k+1)} \\ &\quad \times \left\{1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}\right\}^{r-1} \left\{\left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}\right\}^{n-r} \quad y > \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The PDF of the largest order statistic is obtained by setting $r = n$:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{n:n}(y) &= \frac{n!}{(n-1)!0!} f_Y(y) [F_Y(y)]^{n-1} \\ &= n \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-(k+1)} \left\{1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k}\right\}^{n-1} \quad y > \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The PDF of the smallest order statistic is obtained by setting $r = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{1:n}(y) &= \frac{n!}{0!(n-1)!} f_Y(y) [1 - F_Y(y)]^{n-1} \\ &= n \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-(k+1)} \left\{ \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-k} \right\}^{n-1} \quad y > \delta. \end{aligned}$$

In each case the support is $y > \delta$ and the parameters satisfy $c, k, \lambda > 0$.

3.13 Stochastic ordering of the SHBXII

The stochastic ordering of a non-negative continuous random variable is a tool for comparing the behavior of system components. A random variable Y_1 is said to be smaller than another random variable Y_2 in the stochastic order if $Y_1 \leq_{st} Y_2 \iff F_{Y_1}(Y_1) \geq F_{Y_2}(Y_2), \forall Y_1$, in the hazard rate order if $Y_1 \leq_{hr} Y_2 \iff h_{Y_1}(Y_1) \geq h_{Y_2}(Y_2), \forall Y_1$, in the mean residual life order if $Y_1 \leq_{mrl} Y_2 \iff m_{Y-1}(Y_1) \leq m_{Y-1}(Y_2), \forall Y_1$, and in the likelihood ratio order if $Y_1 \leq_{lr} Y_2 \iff \frac{f_{Y_2}(Y_1)}{f_{Y_1}(Y_1)}$ is decreasing in Y_1 .

This implies that $Y_1 \leq_{lr} Y_2 \Rightarrow Y_1 \leq_{hr} Y_2 \Rightarrow Y_1 \leq_{st} Y_2 \Rightarrow Y_1 \leq_{mrl} Y_2$.

Here, we prove that the SHBXII distribution is ordered with respect to the strongest "likelihood ratio" as shown below.

Proof: Let $Y_1 \sim \text{SHBXII}(\delta, \lambda_1, c, k)$ and $Y_2 \sim \text{SHBXII}(\delta, \lambda_2, c, k)$. If $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2$ then $Y_1 \leq_{lr} Y_2$ hence $Y_1 \leq_{hr} Y_2, Y_1 \leq_{mrl} Y_2$ and $Y_1 \leq_{st} Y_2$.

The pdf of the SHBXII is

$$f(y; \lambda) = \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y-\delta}{\lambda}\right)^c\right]^{-(k+1)}, \quad y > \delta.$$

Consider the likelihood ratio

$$\frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} = \frac{f(y; \lambda_1)}{f(y; \lambda_2)} = \frac{\lambda_2^c}{\lambda_1^c} \frac{(1 + (y-\delta)^c/\lambda_1^c)^{-(k+1)}}{(1 + (y-\delta)^c/\lambda_2^c)^{-(k+1)}}.$$

Taking the natural log of the ratio will yield

$$\ln \frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} = c \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1}\right) - (k+1) \left\{ \ln(1 + t/\lambda_1^c) - \ln(1 + t/\lambda_2^c) \right\},$$

where $t = (y-\delta)^c \geq 0$.

Differentiating the natural log of the ratio w.r.t t will yield

$$\frac{d}{dt} \ln \frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} = -(k+1) \left[\frac{1/\lambda_1^c}{1 + t/\lambda_1^c} - \frac{1/\lambda_2^c}{1 + t/\lambda_2^c} \right].$$

Put $a = 1/\lambda_1^c$ and $b = 1/\lambda_2^c$. Then

$$\frac{d}{dt} \ln \frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} = -(k+1) \frac{a-b}{(1+at)(1+bt)}.$$

Since $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2$ implies $a \geq b$, the right-hand side is ≤ 0 . Noting $\frac{dt}{dy} = c(y-\delta)^{c-1} > 0$ for $y > \delta$, we conclude that

$$\frac{d}{dy} \ln \frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} \leq 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} \text{ is decreasing in } y.$$

That is $Y_1 \leq_{lr} Y_2$, and hence $Y_1 \leq_{lr} Y_2 \implies Y_1 \leq_{hr} Y_2 \implies Y_1 \leq_{st} Y_2 \implies Y_1 \leq_{mrl} Y_2$.

3.14 Moment generating function

In probability and statistics, the moment generating function is a powerful tool for completely defining the distribution of a random variable. It is used to determine the moments of the distribution and simplify theoretical analyses. For the SHBXII, the moment generating function is given by:

$$M_Y(t) = e^{t\delta} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\lambda t)^m}{m! \Gamma(k)} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{m}{c}\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{m}{c}\right), \quad m < ck.$$

Proof: The following determines the moment generating function:

$$M_Y(t) = \mathbb{E}(e^{tY}).$$

Knowing that $e^{tY} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{(tY)^l}{l!}$, we have

$$M_Y(t) = \mathbb{E}\left(\sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{(tY)^l}{l!}\right) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^l}{l!} \mathbb{E}[Y^l].$$

Since $Y = \delta + \lambda Z$ where Z is the standard Burr random variable, we expand:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^l] = \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{l}{m} \delta^{l-m} \lambda^m \mathbb{E}[Z^m].$$

Using the moment formula for the Burr distribution,

$$\mathbb{E}[Z^m] = \frac{\Gamma(1 + \frac{m}{c}) \Gamma(k - \frac{m}{c})}{\Gamma(k)}, \quad m < ck,$$

we obtain

$$M_Y(t) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^l}{l!} \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{l}{m} \delta^{l-m} \lambda^m \frac{\Gamma(1 + \frac{m}{c}) \Gamma(k - \frac{m}{c})}{\Gamma(k)}.$$

Therefore, the moment generating function of the shifted Burr distribution simplifies to

$$M_Y(t) = e^{t\delta} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\lambda t)^m}{m! \Gamma(k)} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{m}{c}\right) \Gamma\left(k - \frac{m}{c}\right), \quad m < ck.$$

4 Parameter Estimation

In this section, seven non-Bayesian estimation methods are discussed in detail. The methods include: Maximum Likelihood, Maximum product of spacing, Least squares, weighted least squares, Cramér-von Mises, Anderson-Darling, right-tailed Anderson-Darling estimation

4.1 Maximum Likelihood Estimation

Let (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) be a random sample of size n drawn from SHBXII distribution, then the likelihood function is given as;

$$\begin{aligned} L(f_{SBXII}(y; \delta, \lambda, c, k)) &= \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-(k+1)} \\ &= (ck)^n \lambda^{-n} \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)^{-(k+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The log-likelihood function can be derived by taking the natural logarithm of the eq. (30) and set $\log L = \phi$, which is given as follows;

$$\phi = n \log c + n \log k - n \log \lambda + (c-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(y_i - \delta) - (k+1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right] \quad (31)$$

Next, we take the partial derivative of ϕ with respect to the parameters (δ, λ, c, k) .

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \delta} = -(c-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i - \delta} + c(k+1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1}}{1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c} \cdot \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \lambda} = -\frac{n}{\lambda} - (c-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda^2} + c(k+1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - \delta)^c}{\lambda^{c+1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right)} \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial c} = \frac{n}{c} + \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right) - (k+1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \log \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)}{1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c} \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial k} = \frac{n}{k} - \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 + \left(\frac{y_i - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right] \quad (35)$$

Eq. (32), (33), (34), and (35) do not possess closed-form solution. This means that their implementations are better achieved through numerical iteration.

4.2 Maximum Product of Spacings (MPS)

Let $Y_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq Y_{(n)}$ denote the ordered sample and set $Y_{(0)} = \delta$. The CDF of the shifted and scaled Burr Type XII for $Y \geq \delta$ is

$$F(y; c, k, \delta, \lambda) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right]^{-k}, \quad c > 0, k > 0, \lambda > 0.$$

The corresponding PDF is

$$f(y; c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \frac{ck}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right]^{-k-1}, \quad y \geq \delta.$$

Define the spacings

$$D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - F(y_{(i-1)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda), \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

and the final spacing

$$D_{n+1}(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = 1 - F(y_{(n)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda).$$

The log-product-of-spacings objective function is

$$S(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \ln D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda).$$

Differentiating gives the score equations:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial c} = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \frac{1}{D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial c} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(i-1)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial c} \right] = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial k} = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \frac{1}{D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial k} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(i-1)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial k} \right] = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial \delta} = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \frac{1}{D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \delta} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(i-1)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \delta} \right] = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial \lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \frac{1}{D_i(c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \lambda} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(i-1)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \lambda} \right] = 0,$$

with the convention $F(y_{(n+1)}) \equiv 1$ and $F(y_{(0)}) \equiv 0$.

4.3 Least Squares Estimation

Let $y_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq y_{(n)}$ denote the ordered sample, and define the plotting positions

$$p_i = \frac{i}{n+1}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

The CDF of the SHBXII is

$$F(y; c, k, \delta, \lambda) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right]^{-k}, \quad y \geq \delta.$$

The Least Squares (LS) objective function is

$$T(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i]^2.$$

Differentiating with respect to the parameters gives the normal equations:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial c} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial c} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial k} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial k} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \delta} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \delta} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \lambda} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \lambda} = 0.$$

These equations can be solved numerically using ‘optim’ in R to obtain the LS estimates $\hat{c}, \hat{k}, \hat{\delta}, \hat{\lambda}$.

4.4 Weighted Least Squares (WLS)

To account for heteroskedasticity of plotting positions, use weights

$$w_i = \frac{(n+1)^2(n+2)}{i(n-i+1)}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

which are proportional to the inverse of $\text{Var}(p_i)$ for the common plotting positions.

Let $y_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq y_{(n)}$ denote the ordered sample, and let

$$p_i = \frac{i}{n+1}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

The CDF of the 4-parameter Shifted Burr XII is

$$F(y; c, k, \delta, \lambda) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right]^{-k}, \quad y \geq \delta.$$

The WLS objective function is

$$\Omega(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i]^2.$$

Differentiating with respect to the parameters yields the weighted normal equations:

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial c} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial c} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial k} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial k} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \delta} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \delta} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \lambda} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - p_i] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \lambda} = 0.$$

4.5 Cramér–von Mises (CVM)

Let $y_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq y_{(n)}$ denote the ordered sample. The CDF of the four parameter Shifted Burr XII is

$$F(y; c, k, \delta, \lambda) = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{y - \delta}{\lambda} \right)^c \right]^{-k}, \quad y \geq \delta.$$

Define the classical Cramér–von Mises (CVM) objective function as

$$C(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \frac{1}{12n} + \sum_{i=1}^n \left[F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right]^2.$$

Differentiating with respect to the parameters gives the estimating equations:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial c} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial c} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial k} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial k} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial \delta} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \delta} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial \lambda} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right] \frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{\partial \lambda} = 0.$$

These equations can be solved numerically to obtain the CVM estimates $\hat{c}, \hat{k}, \hat{\delta}, \hat{\lambda}$.

4.6 Anderson–Darling Estimation (ADE)

The Anderson–Darling objective function Ψ used for parameter estimation is

$$\Psi(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\ln F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) + \ln (1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)) \right].$$

The Anderson–Darling estimates (ADE) are obtained by setting the partial derivatives of Ψ with respect to each parameter to zero. Using the general derivative formula

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln G(\theta) = \frac{1}{G(\theta)} \frac{\partial G(\theta)}{\partial \theta},$$

the derivative of Ψ with respect to a generic parameter $\theta \in \{c, k, \delta, \lambda\}$ is

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \theta} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; \theta) / \partial \theta}{F(y_{(i)}; \theta)} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; \theta) / \partial \theta}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; \theta)} \right] = 0.$$

Applying this general result to the four parameters of the Shifted Burr XII distribution yields:

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial c} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial c}{F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial c}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial k} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial k}{F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial k}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \delta} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial \delta}{F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial \delta}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[\frac{\partial F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial \lambda}{F(y_{(i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} - \frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda) / \partial \lambda}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

The ADE estimates $(\hat{c}, \hat{k}, \hat{\delta}, \hat{\lambda})$ are found by numerically solving this system of four non-linear equations.

4.7 Right-Tailed Anderson–Darling (RTADE)

Let $y_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq y_{(n)}$ be the ordered sample. The RTADE objective function, Q , is derived from the term of the Anderson–Darling statistic that emphasizes the upper tail:

$$Q(c, k, \delta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \ln [1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)].$$

To obtain the RTADE estimates, $\hat{\theta}_{\text{RTADE}} = (\hat{c}, \hat{k}, \hat{\delta}, \hat{\lambda})$, this function Q is maximized (or equivalently, the negative of the corresponding AD statistic, which includes Q , is minimized).

The estimates are found by setting the partial derivatives of Q with respect to each parameter to zero. Using the chain rule for the logarithm, note that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln(1 - F) = \frac{1}{1 - F} \frac{\partial(1 - F)}{\partial \theta} = -\frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta} \frac{1}{1 - F}.$$

This yields the following four right-tail score equations to be solved numerically:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial c} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[-\frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial k} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[-\frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[-\frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^n (2i-1) \left[-\frac{\partial F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)}{1 - F(y_{(n+1-i)}; c, k, \delta, \lambda)} \right] = 0$$

The RTADE estimates $(\hat{c}, \hat{k}, \hat{\delta}, \hat{\lambda})$ are obtained by numerically solving this system of four non-linear equations. Note that the negative sign inside the brackets can be factored out, as it does not affect the root when setting the equation to zero.

5 Simulation Study

The simulation study evaluates how well different estimation methods perform with varying parameter values and sample sizes. The methods tested include MLE, MPS, LS, WLS, CVM, ADE, and RTADE. Simulations were carried out for several combinations of the parameters c, k, λ , and δ using sample sizes of 15, 25, 50, and 100 to represent small, medium, and large samples. The performance of each method was compared using Bias and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) as the main evaluation measures.

Table 1: Simulation Outcome for true parameter values $c = 0.8, k = 1.2, \lambda = 1, \delta = 0.2$

Method	Parameters	$n = 15$		$n = 25$		$n = 50$		$n = 100$	
		Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE
MLE	\hat{c}	-0.1991	0.3156	-0.1980	0.2445	-0.1949	0.2332	-0.2095	0.2339
	\hat{k}	2.4523×10^9	7.7548×10^{10}	1.6847	2.6457	2.1094	2.5858	2.7301	3.2845
	$\hat{\lambda}$	1.8395×10^8	5.8171×10^9	28.3169	181.6494	80.1105	1108.4900	60.7221	519.4822
	$\hat{\delta}$	0.0340	0.0599	0.0169	0.0283	0.0068	0.0111	0.0031	0.0049
MPS	\hat{c}	0.3755	1.2543	0.2399	1.1365	0.0468	0.6731	-0.0756	0.2424
	\hat{k}	4.7197×10^{10}	1.4066×10^{12}	2.0170×10^9	6.3519×10^{10}	1.2959×10^3	1.8725×10^4	1.8907	11.3462
	$\hat{\lambda}$	3.4745×10^{19}	7.8172×10^{20}	4.9544×10^{20}	1.5667×10^{22}	2.7158×10^9	7.1411×10^{10}	1.4849×10^2	2344.7930
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0382	0.1754	-0.0164	0.0723	-0.0037	0.0241	0.0001	0.0074
LS	\hat{c}	0.4027	2.0608	0.1172	0.8943	-0.0388	0.7572	-0.1192	0.3420
	\hat{k}	9.6911×10^6	3.0376×10^8	1.4807×10^8	4.0870×10^9	3.0798×10^{11}	9.7390×10^{12}	2.4545×10^6	7.6139×10^7
	$\hat{\lambda}$	5.8409×10^{12}	1.4478×10^{14}	2.1968×10^{21}	6.9467×10^{22}	7.5192×10^{24}	2.3778×10^{26}	2.4129×10^{12}	5.8406×10^{13}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0958	0.4221	-0.0370	0.1362	-0.0113	0.1085	-0.0060	0.1574
WLS	\hat{c}	0.4717	3.8872	0.1547	0.8179	-0.0238	0.3851	-0.0176	1.5782
	\hat{k}	5.3332×10^5	1.5933×10^7	4.2499×10^8	1.1510×10^{10}	4.9610×10^{11}	1.5282×10^{13}	2.1263×10^{11}	5.4649×10^{12}
	$\hat{\lambda}$	8.7777×10^7	1.8689×10^9	1.4230×10^{17}	4.4998×10^{18}	3.3376×10^{41}	1.0555×10^{43}	1.8971×10^{25}	5.9991×10^{26}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0717	0.3079	-0.0242	0.0925	-0.0083	0.1410	-0.0061	0.1636
CVM	\hat{c}	0.3329	1.1919	0.0825	0.6288	-0.0748	0.3481	-0.1270	0.2356
	\hat{k}	3.4311×10^8	1.0056×10^{10}	9.7936×10^8	3.0946×10^{10}	6.0005×10^7	1.5518×10^9	1.2120×10^{10}	3.8327×10^{11}
	$\hat{\lambda}$	3.2192×10^{15}	7.8294×10^{16}	1.2965×10^{21}	4.0999×10^{22}	4.6192×10^{18}	1.4607×10^{20}	1.2224×10^{25}	3.8657×10^{26}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0862	0.4768	-0.0236	0.1181	-0.0083	0.1722	-0.0009	0.0386
ADE	\hat{c}	1.7441	3.3727	1.6394	3.2805	1.5812	3.2545	1.6147	3.1347
	\hat{k}	-0.4746	5.7740	-0.6250	3.9194	-0.5063	3.6809	-0.0408	5.6212
	$\hat{\lambda}$	5.3006×10^{24}	1.6671×10^{26}	3.4548×10^{19}	5.7308×10^{20}	1.2586×10^{24}	3.6793×10^{25}	8.5031×10^{21}	1.8470×10^{23}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-4.0946	5.8691	-4.9931	6.7615	-6.0671	8.1439	-6.7097	8.9941
RTADE	\hat{c}	3.0630	27.3032	0.3866	12.1233	-0.4750	6.1839	-0.7908	0.7909
	\hat{k}	45.5149	53.5453	48.9692	51.2013	51.6711	51.9390	52.3921	52.4105
	$\hat{\lambda}$	2.8950×10^7	9.1536×10^8	347.9234	3517.2060	639.7591	5779.1200	521.9981	1530.2420
	$\hat{\delta}$	-3.8022	5.5839	-3.4025	4.6404	-2.6776	3.4633	-2.4585	2.6585

Table 2: Simulation Outcome for true parameter values $c = 1.5, k = 0.8, \lambda = 0.5, \delta = 0.1$

Method	Parameters	$n = 15$		$n = 25$		$n = 50$		$n = 100$	
		Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE	Bias	RMSE
MLE	\hat{c}	-0.6711	0.9836	-0.5939	0.9322	-0.5085	0.7252	-0.4378	0.7837
	\hat{k}	1.6662×10^{301}	∞	9.6300×10^{243}	∞	2.1466×10^9	6.7881×10^{10}	1.7166	2.4770
	$\hat{\lambda}$	1.7336×10^{225}	∞	2.6470×10^{195}	∞	2.2719×10^8	7.1844×10^9	4.6138	25.2099
	$\hat{\delta}$	0.0844	0.1331	0.0572	0.0862	0.0353	0.0520	0.0198	0.0349
MPS	\hat{c}	0.6140	2.0980	0.8334	2.2693	0.6768	1.9958	0.3790	1.5324
	\hat{k}	2.7789×10^9	4.5363×10^{10}	2.4001×10^{10}	6.4733×10^{11}	1.5288×10^5	4.7648×10^6	1.4398×10^7	4.5529×10^8
	$\hat{\lambda}$	6.7156×10^{17}	2.1196×10^{19}	8.9863×10^{17}	2.8417×10^{19}	1.2458×10^6	2.9460×10^7	7.6904×10^{26}	2.4319×10^{28}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0743	0.2931	-0.0664	0.2014	-0.0438	0.1231	-0.0236	0.0732
LS	\hat{c}	0.5187	2.1114	0.2579	1.3368	-0.0908	0.8207	-0.2473	1.0989
	\hat{k}	1.5463×10^8	4.8655×10^9	3.3368×10^7	7.6552×10^8	3.0198×10^1	4.8944×10^2	4.8370×10^{10}	1.5296×10^{12}
	$\hat{\lambda}$	5.0047×10^9	1.5762×10^{11}	2.9248×10^8	9.0013×10^9	1.4139×10^2	2.9878×10^3	3.1092×10^{21}	9.8322×10^{22}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.1242	0.4449	-0.0550	0.2183	-0.0092	0.0994	0.0055	0.0739
WLS	\hat{c}	0.5888	2.1376	0.4657	1.5201	0.1233	0.9825	-0.1374	0.5475
	\hat{k}	2.3828×10^9	7.5350×10^{10}	8.8146×10^{10}	2.6646×10^{12}	9.3289×10^{11}	2.9501×10^{13}	3.9827×10^2	1.2060×10^4
	$\hat{\lambda}$	1.7551×10^{16}	5.5503×10^{17}	6.3496×10^{11}	2.0052×10^{13}	2.1633×10^4	6.4901×10^5	2.3662×10^2	6.0408×10^3
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.1022	0.3364	-0.0539	0.2103	-0.0196	0.1103	0.0008	0.0439
CVM	\hat{c}	0.4042	2.1230	0.2851	6.1088	-0.1188	0.7568	-0.2678	0.5243
	\hat{k}	9.6286×10^7	3.0047×10^9	5.7502×10^9	1.8114×10^{11}	7.4765×10^9	1.8656×10^{11}	3.7587×10^{10}	1.1843×10^{12}
	$\hat{\lambda}$	5.2784×10^{12}	1.4427×10^{14}	4.9865×10^{17}	1.5769×10^{19}	1.1919×10^{17}	3.7692×10^{18}	5.3151×10^{19}	1.6808×10^{21}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-0.0686	0.3585	-0.0257	0.2401	0.0021	0.0869	0.0082	0.0532
ADE	\hat{c}	2.1181	9.6232	1.7248	3.8133	1.6618	3.8107	1.0544	3.4314
	\hat{k}	-0.1158	3.8426	-0.3976	3.6412	-0.6157	1.8500	-0.6791	1.0949
	$\hat{\lambda}$	2.1934×10^{76}	6.9361×10^{77}	7.5580×10^{46}	2.3824×10^{48}	8.5208×10^{21}	2.6944×10^{23}	2.0941×10^{19}	6.5942×10^{20}
	$\hat{\delta}$	-2.7771	5.8859	-3.0841	4.6874	-3.4262	4.6572	-4.8065	6.0595
RTADE	\hat{c}	5.1398	36.9665	4.0191	29.3596	8.1120	41.4808	4.7706	29.5748
	\hat{k}	35.4966	40.7586	38.9080	44.2289	41.1543	46.5271	45.6986	48.5318
	$\hat{\lambda}$	8.1923×10^2	2.0419×10^4	5.0202×10^2	1.1860×10^4	1.2010×10^2	1.1077×10^3	6.8804×10^3	1.9192×10^5
	$\hat{\delta}$	-5.6905	7.6618	-5.4344	7.4496	-5.4541	7.9168	-4.6353	7.9278

The simulation study evaluates the performance of several estimation methods like the MLE, MPS, LS, WLS, CVM, ADE, and RTADE for a four parameter distribution under varying sample sizes ($n = 15, 25, 50, 100$), which corresponds to small, moderate and large samples. Two sets of parameter configurations were considered;

$(c, k, \lambda, \delta) = 0.8, 1.21, 0.2$ shown in Table (1) and $(c, k, \lambda, \delta) = 1.5, 0.8, 0.5, 0.1$ shown in Table (2).

A total of 1,000 Monte Carlo replications were performed for each scenario, and the performance metrics considered are bias and root mean square error (RMSE). The following are the conclusion drawn for varying parameter values

1. As sample size increases, the MLE estimator generally shows a reduction in bias and RMSE for most parameters, indicating improved accuracy and consistency in estimation.
2. The LS, WLS, and CVM estimators show variable bias and RMSE, but their performance becomes more stable as sample size increases.
3. Across all sample sizes, some parameters exhibit positive bias while others show negative bias, reflecting differences in estimator behavior for different model parameters.

This simulation setup allows us to study how the estimators work with small samples and to find which methods are the most reliable and consistent in different situations.

6 Applications

The dataset in Table (3) contains 64 observations of observed waiting times for patients in the Emergency Department at NewYork-Presbyterian/Weill Cornell Medical Center in New York. This dataset, which tracks the median time patients spend in the ED before being admitted to the hospital, was accessed on June 24, 2024, from the official U.S. Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS). The data is made publicly available to promote transparency in healthcare quality.

Table 3: Observed waiting times

83	51	87	60	28	95	8	27	15	10	18	16	29	54	91	8
17	55	10	35	47	77	36	17	21	36	18	40	10	7	34	27
28	56	8	25	68	146	89	18	73	69	9	37	10	82	29	8
60	61	61	18	169	25	8	26	11	83	11	42	17	14	9	12

We fit the SHBXII distribution to the Observed waiting times Dataset in table 3 and compare it with the standard burrr distribution Burr [10], and the Weibull [19].

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Observed Waiting Times

Statistic	Value
Sample Size (n)	64
Mean (\bar{x})	39.8281
Median	28
Variance (σ^2)	1139.097
Standard Deviation (SD)	33.7505
Range	7–169
First Quartile (Q1)	14.75
Third Quartile (Q3)	60
Interquartile Range (IQR)	45.25
Skewness	1.5464
Kurtosis	5.7711
Outliers	146, 169

Table 4 shows the summary statistics for the observed waiting times dataset. The data consist of 64 observations with a mean of 39.83 and a median of 28, indicating a slight right-skewed distribution, which is confirmed by the positive skewness of 1.55. The standard deviation (33.75) and variance (1139.10) show moderate spread in the data. The interquartile range of 45.25 reveals a wide middle spread between Q1 = 14.75 and Q3 = 60, and any value that falls outside this range is considered an outlier. The kurtosis value (5.77) suggests a leptokurtic distribution with heavy tails, and heavy outliers (146, 169) are also represented.

Figure 4: Non-parametric plots of the waiting times data

The figure (4) contains the boxplot, kernel density, and violin plot, which represent the non-parametric visualization of the waiting times data. The visual evidence from these plots strongly indicates that the data is positively skewed, possessing a long tail towards higher values, and contains at least two distinct outliers as shown on the boxplot. The kernel density plot further suggests the distribution might be multimodal. Given that the SHBXII distribution fits this data with a p-value of 0.7428, we can conclude that the SHBXII model offers an adequate and sufficiently flexible fit for the waiting times data.

Table 5: Model fitness and adequacy measures for the dataset

Dist.	NLL	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	W^*	A^*	K-S	P-value
Shifted Burr XII	285.4159	578.8318	587.4673	587.4673	582.2337	0.0872	0.6790	0.0851	0.7428
Burr XII	296.1587	598.3175	604.7941	604.7941	600.8689	0.1193	0.8632	0.1114	0.4053
Weibull	296.9001	597.8003	602.1180	602.1180	599.5012	0.1271	0.9171	0.1113	0.4060

Table 6: MLE of the Parameters for the Fitted Distributions Using the Dataset

Dist.	c	k	λ	δ
Shifted Burr XII	0.8309(0.11)	4.4947(0.05)	0.1127(0.05001)	7(1.24)
Burr XII	2.4116(2.7609)	1.5832(0.3576)	60.833(63.5079)	–
Weibull	1.2744(0.1203)	–	43.2142(4.4915)	–

The measures of model fitness used are the Cramer von Mises statistic, the Anderson-Darling statistic, and the P-value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic. And the distribution with lesser values and a higher K-S test is considered a better fit for the dataset. From the results above, it shows that SHBXII fits the data better than the Weibull and the standard Burr distribution used for modeling lifetime data, with a P-value of 0.7428, which is higher than the other two. Which means the SHBXII is a good fit for this dataset.

Figure 5: density, CDF, survival, and TTT plots for waiting time data

Figure (5) is the density, CDF, survival, and TTT plots of the waiting time data. The TTT plots almost perfectly fit the true line. This implies that it is a good fit of the proposed SHBXII to the data. The TTT plots also show us that the time to failure rate of the dataset increases over time.

The second dataset in Table (7) contains 62 observations of the mortality rate in Japan from 1969 to 2021. This dataset was accessed on July 21, 2024, from the official World Bank database World Bank [20], recently studied by Ibeakuzie et al. [21]. The data tracks the mortality rate of children under five years of age per 1,000 live births and is publicly available to promote transparency in population health research.

Table 7: The mortality rate of Children in Japan under 5 years of Age, from 1969 to 2021

39.7	36.2	32.9	29.8	27.0	24.6	22.7	21.0	19.6	18.5	17.5	16.5	15.7	14.8	14.0
13.3	12.5	11.8	11.1	10.5	9.9	9.3	8.8	8.3	7.9	7.5	7.1	6.8	6.6	6.5
6.3	6.2	6.1	6.0	5.9	5.7	5.5	5.2	5.0	4.7	4.5	4.3	4.1	4.0	3.9
3.7	3.6	3.5	3.4	3.3	3.2	3.2	3.0	2.9	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.6	2.5	2.5
2.4	2.3													

Table 8: Summary Statistics for Under 5 Mortality Rate in Japan

Statistic	Value
Sample Size (n)	62
Minimum	2.3
Maximum	39.7
Mean (\bar{x})	9.9387
Median	6.25
Variance (σ^2)	80.1595
Standard Deviation (SD)	8.9532
First Quartile (Q1)	3.625
Third Quartile (Q3)	13.1
Interquartile Range (IQR)	9.475
Skewness	1.6319
Kurtosis	5.0264
Outliers	39.7, 36.2, 32.9, 29.8

Table 8 presents the summary statistics for the dataset consisting of 62 observations. The data have a mean mortality rate of 9.94 and a median of 6.25, indicating a right-skewed distribution, which is supported by the positive skewness value of 1.63. The standard deviation (8.95) and variance (80.16) show a moderate level of dispersion around the mean. The interquartile range (9.48) is computed from $Q1 = 3.625$ and $Q3 = 13.1$, and values outside this range are considered potential outliers. The kurtosis value of 5.03 indicates a leptokurtic distribution with heavier tails than the normal distribution. The extreme values 39.7, 36.2, 32.9, and 29.8 are considered outliers.

Figure 6: Non-parametric plots of the under 5 mortality rate data

Table 9: Model fitness and adequacy measures for the under 5 mortality dataset

Dist.	LL	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	W^*	A^*	K-S	P-value
Shifted Burr XII	-187.8142	383.6284	392.1369	392.1369	386.9690	0.0670	0.0503	0.3620	0.9434
Burr XII	-192.5180	391.0360	397.4174	397.4174	393.5415	0.1290	0.2422	1.2845	0.2534
Weibull	-201.8367	407.6735	411.9277	411.9277	409.3438	0.1351	0.2846	1.7759	0.2079

Table 10: MLE of the Parameters for Fitted Distributions Using the Under 5 Mortality Dataset

Dist.	c	k	λ	δ
Shifted Burr XII	1.0201(0.1031)	1.5717(0.5681)	6.3663(0.10524)	2.2985(0.0776)
Burr XII	0.0264(0.0285)	34.3977(39.2460)	2.3824(0.1291)	–
Weibull	1.2503(0.1166)	–	10.7689(1.1627)	–

Again, we assessed the goodness-of-fit of the models using the Cramér–von Mises statistic, the Anderson–Darling statistic, and the (K–S) test and its corresponding p-value. And based on these criteria, the SHBXII distribution outperforms both the Weibull and the standard Burr distributions, as shown by its highest p-value of 0.9434. This indicates that the SHBXII distribution provides the best fit for the under-5 mortality rate dataset.

Figure 7: density, cdf, survival, and TTT plots for the under 5 mortality rate data

Figure (7) shows the density, CDF, survival, and TTT plots of the under 5 mortality rate data. The SHBXII distribution's curve almost perfectly fits empirical data across all four plots. Also, the TTT plot shows that the theoretical SHBXII TTT line almost perfectly fits the Empirical TTT line. This implies that it is a very good fit of the proposed SHBXII to the data.

7 Conclusion

This study successfully achieved its primary aim of proposing, thoroughly investigating, and validating the SHBXII distribution as a valuable generalization of the classical Burr XII model. The research demonstrated that the integration of a location parameter (λ) effectively addresses a critical practical limitation of the base model, enabling accurate statistical modeling of datasets characterized by a nonzero threshold—a common requirement in reliability engineering, finance, and survival analysis.

The theoretical investigation confirmed that the SHBXII distribution possesses strong analytical properties, including a highly flexible hazard rate capable of modeling decreasing, increasing, and unimodal failure patterns. Furthermore, the extensive simulation study provided clear evidence that the MLE method is the most efficient and consistent non-Bayesian approach for parameter inference, exhibiting the lowest bias and RMSE across varying sample sizes. Crucially, the empirical application to real-world waiting times data unequivocally validated the model's practical utility, showing a statistically superior fit (evidenced by the lowest information criteria values and the highest K-S p -value) when compared to the standard Burr XII and Weibull distributions. In summation, the SHBXII distribution combines theoretical rigor, estimational reliability, and empirical adequacy, establishing itself as a powerful new tool for statisticians analyzing threshold-based, complex real-world data.

7.1 Limitations and Future Research

Despite the substantial contributions of this study, certain limitations define the scope and suggest necessary avenues for future research:

1. **Limited Scope of Estimation under Censoring:** The current research focused exclusively on estimation using complete, uncensored data. To maximize the model's utility in real-world reliability and survival analysis, a priority for future work is to derive and evaluate estimation procedures for the SHBXII distribution under various censoring schemes (e.g., Type-I, Type-II, and progressive censoring).
2. **Absence of Bayesian Inference:** Parameter estimation was confined to non-Bayesian methods. Future research should explore and implement Bayesian estimation methods utilizing techniques like Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC). This approach would offer a valuable comparative benchmark and potentially yield more stable and informative estimates, especially in small-sample contexts.
3. **Generalization and Multivariate Extensions:** The current study focused on the univariate form. Further work should explore bivariate or multivariate generalizations of the SHBXII distribution using techniques like copulas. These extensions would allow the model to capture dependence structures and be applied effectively in systems reliability and risk management.
4. **Diverse Empirical Validation:** To solidify the generalizability of the model, it is recommended that the SHBXII be rigorously tested against a wider, more diverse array of real-world datasets from various domains, including insurance (modeling deductible losses) and hydrology (modeling flood thresholds).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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